

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386300826>

Improving asset management in capital-intensive industries: Case study of a Portuguese water utility

Article in *Utilities Policy* · December 2024

DOI: 10.1016/j.jup.2024.101822

CITATIONS

0

READS

12

4 authors, including:

Flavia Barbosa

Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science (INESC TEC)

24 PUBLICATIONS 123 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Full-length article

Improving asset management in capital-intensive industries: Case study of a Portuguese water utility

Mariana Casalta ^{a,b,*}, Flávia Barbosa ^{a,b}, Luciana Yamada ^{a,b}, Lígia B. Ramos ^c

^a Faculdade de Engenharia, Universidade do Porto, Portugal

^b INESC TEC, Porto, Portugal

^c Águas do Douro e Paiva, S.A., Portugal

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Asset management (AM)

Optimisation

Water service

ABSTRACT

The efficient management of assets delivers value and is essential for achieving service objectives, managing risks, and reducing costs. This paper proposes decision-support methods to help capital-intensive industries manage their assets and optimise their life cycle. Optimisation approaches were developed to support long-term investment planning by maximising the value created and minimising the budget used. Also, the trade-off for both objectives was analysed. Using the proposed models will lead to efficient management of available capital and excellent service delivery. Thus, water companies will fulfil the regulator's requirements and present well-founded decision-making. This study was applied to a Portuguese water utility.

1. Introduction

Water is a limited natural resource that is indispensable for individual well-being. Water service managers must ensure the efficient and rational management of clean water and the provision of quality service (Vilarinho et al., 2023c). The lack of a safe and adequate water service has inevitable consequences for public health, the economy, and the environment (Alegre et al., 2020). In this sense, Goal 6 of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) seeks to "ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all", recognising the importance of this primary service (United Nations, 2024).

Urban water systems are highly capital-intensive and constitute public infrastructure of enormous value. Utilities and municipalities manage these critical assets and optimise their performance. These infrastructures should function properly during all their useful life; however, they increasingly show signs of ageing and degradation. In contrast, over time, society imposes greater demands on the service provided, risk management, and sustainability (Alegre and Coelho, 2012).

The ERSAR (Water and Waste Services Regulation Authority) regulates water supply, wastewater and waste management services in Portugal. It supervises the behaviour of water operators, establishing performance indicators and collecting data for each operator. It also makes public the activity plan, the available budget for each year, the annual report on operations and regulatory and supervisory activity,

the management report and the respective accounts. The public presentation of the results exposes the operators' performance, promoting improvements in the sector (Marques and Pinto, 2018). In this sense, water utilities have implemented policies favouring asset management (AM) principles, to achieve business goals and better returns. Effective AM is essential and represents a priority to guarantee that the asset value is managed correctly, ensuring adequate and sustainable levels of water services in the long term (Kang, 2019).

The water sector must become more resilient in the face of uncertainties, such as limited financial resources, the loss of skilled labour through retirement, and extreme weather conditions, and are expected to be managed for current and future generations (Alegre et al., 2020). In the view of Shafer and Fox (2017), the hybrid crises constitute one of the most significant risks we currently face. The unsustainability of current water systems is increasingly evident due to human-caused climate change (Gleick, 2018; Trindade et al., 2020; Rising et al., 2022).

This way, water utility managers are challenged to decide which assets should be rehabilitated to meet public demand efficiently. At the same time, their decisions must guarantee a quality service delivery to their consumers without jeopardising the financial integrity of the water utilities (Ferreira and Carriço, 2019). These utilities must design policies and efficient investment strategies to support AM principles. These policies comprise planning and defining long-term investments and prioritising the budget. It will improve the infrastructure performance and optimise their decisions over the asset life cycle. Rezvani et al. (2022). Adversities are present in managing water utilities

* Corresponding author at: Faculdade de Engenharia, Universidade do Porto, Portugal.

E-mail addresses: up201605416@edu.fe.up.pt (M. Casalta), flavia.barbosa@inesctec.pt (F. Barbosa), luciana.o.yamada@inesctec.pt (L. Yamada), ligiaramos@adp.pt (L.B. Ramos).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2024.101822>

Received 28 July 2023; Received in revised form 30 August 2024; Accepted 30 August 2024

0957-1787/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

and other capital-intensive industries, which provide essential services for society's quality of life, such as the transportation, energy and communications sectors. [Maletič et al. \(2022\)](#).

The methodology proposed by [Ramos-Salgado et al. \(2022\)](#) addressed several literature gaps about investment prioritisation in water supply and sewer infrastructure. The authors developed an Infrastructure Asset Management (IAM) framework to aid decision-making and efficiently plan the investment needs of water utilities. The methodology establishes a replacement priority for each network asset and defines and monitors key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess infrastructures. In this sense, one of the main goals of water utilities is to define and substantiate specific action plans and long-term investment needs, making this decision simple and accessible to all utilities by integrating an optimisation approach. However, it has not yet been fully explored in the literature, which evoked a strong motivation for this research.

Although there are already several optimisation approaches in the literature, the models implemented in the water industry focus on minimising costs and balancing the performance and risk of the water distribution system (WDS) ([Mailhot et al., 2003](#); [Dandy and Engelhardt, 2006](#); [Hong et al., 2006](#); [Mann and Frey, 2011](#); [Rokstad and Ugarelli, 2015](#); [Ricalde et al., 2022](#)). This work focuses on the value that the realisation of investments will create for utilities, both in terms of the greater efficiency of the WDS and the positive social impact and compliance with their future legal obligations (e.g. investments planned for network expansion).

This paper proposes an optimisation tool that designs policies to guide investment planning in capital-intensive industries. Two problems are formulated to return the investments that should be made each year of the planning horizon. The first model maximises the value creation by realising investments according to the available annual budget. The second model minimises the budget required to create value through investments. The value classification of investment proposals presents clear criteria at several levels: strategic, technical, economic, political, social, and environmental. In addition, we combine the two optimisation objectives in a third study using evolutionary algorithms. These algorithms help to find almost optimal solutions, providing valuable alternatives for decision-making and establishing a balance between the two approaches.

The formulations can be adapted to other capital-intensive industries. It also offers various contributions, such as optimising and prioritising investments over a given planning horizon, using clear and transparent criteria in decision-making, and enabling the conscious allocation of the utility's capital and resources. In this work, both models are evaluated through a Portuguese water utility case study, which is responsible for the collection, treatment, and supply of water to the population of the south of Greater Porto.

This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents a comprehensive literature review on AM and the principal developments in water industry investment planning. Section 3 formulates the problem and describes the objectives and constraints of two binary linear programming models and a multi-objective approach. Section 4 provides the analysed case study, which illustrates the proposed optimisation model, and the discussion of the obtained results is covered in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions and suggestions for future work.

2. Literature review

In the last few years, AM has become a predominant approach among organisations as an effective tool to ensure the business's sustainability and operations ([Komljenovic et al., 2016](#)). According to ISO 55000, AM is a coordinated activity of an organisation that reflects its objectives in its decisions and plans related to assets to realise and produce value. The value of each asset can be tangible or intangible, financial or non-financial, and considers risk and uncertainty throughout

the life phases (ISO ISO 55000:2014, 2014). Each organisation must determine the meaning of value depending on its objectives, nature, and purpose, and the needs and expectations of its stakeholders ([Institute of Asset Management, 2015](#)).

Effective control and management of assets are essential to addressing risks and investment opportunities by balancing financial, environmental, and social costs, quality of service, and performance (ISO ISO 55000:2014, 2014). It will increase the assets' reliability, availability and security, contributing to higher customer satisfaction and asset value ([Lima and Costa, 2019](#)). In addition, it will impact the population's economic growth and the quality of life and influence all activities of the asset's life cycle, from its conception to its deactivation ([Almeida et al., 2022](#); [El-Akruti et al., 2013](#)).

Capital-intensive industries are increasingly adopting AM principles to overcome challenges, such as ageing infrastructures, strict regulatory operating conditions, maintenance delays, limited financial resources and the loss of skilled labour through retirement. In addition, these industries involve high-value assets and significant capital investment and must ensure a quality service for the consumers. In this sense, a well-defined and structured AM plan can minimise the impacts of these challenges ([Goforth et al., 2022](#)). For this, organisations must make decisions regarding capital investments and the maintenance and operations actions they should carry out on their infrastructures ([Institute of Asset Management, 2015](#)).

As the network ages, reliability decreases in regulated network industries, and the probability of failure increases, resulting in a dispute between asset rehabilitation and maintenance. There are two options available: (i) the utility can replace or rehabilitate an asset at the end of its life or acquire a new asset, which comprises a capital expenditure (CAPEX), or (ii) the utility can perform scheduled maintenance actions on the asset or repair it if it breaks down, which comprises an operating expenditure (OPEX). Whereas OPEX consists of expenditure on short-lived assets that are fully used up during the accounting year, it is not subject to depreciation and does not incur a capital cost. On the other hand, CAPEX is a long-lived investment that will take a long time to be repaid and requires a certain capital expenditure ([Brunekreeft and Rammerstorfer, 2021](#)).

The optimal combination of CAPEX and OPEX is a promising approach, comprising the total expenditure (TOTEX), which makes it possible to support both innovations and to reduce the overall costs associated with the utility's business activity ([Belay et al., 2021](#)).

In addition, managers in these industries should be concerned with adopting customer-centric thinking, identifying the business needs of their consumers and understanding how value is created in their eyes ([Davies, 2004](#)). The operating expenditure costs maintain an asset or repair it if it fails and does not add value to the WDS. However, capital expenditures costs represent investments and can add value when properly executed ([Brunekreeft and Rammerstorfer, 2021](#)).

According to [González-Prida et al. \(2019\)](#), with the generalisation of AM and the support of new information technologies, it is possible to quantify the value created by engineered assets. The concept of utility value must include and describe all the components that portray organisational objectives. The value created by an asset investment can comprise various components such as social impact, impact on other stakeholders, safety, environment, operation, and profits, among many others. Each component has a relative weight in the value composition depending on the utility's vision and mission. However, some of these components require more effort to be evaluated monetarily. Therefore, the methods to solve these situations must be developed, even though they may present high subjectivity and low accuracy.

The American Water Works Association's annual State of the Water Industry survey revealed that rehabilitation and replacement of ageing water infrastructure, long-term availability of potable water supplies and financing for capital improvements have been the main challenges faced by the sector ([AWWA, 2023](#)). Therefore, to optimise the utility's

future investment decisions, key stakeholders such as asset management, operations, long-term planning and environmental management must consolidate and align their individual requirements and strategic objectives. A WDS review should determine current flows and loads, establish available capacity reserves and identify optimisation projects to resolve process bottlenecks. Next, developing a long-term strategic plan that includes future developments, such as demographic growth, technological evolution and climate change, is critical to anticipate these events (Krampe and Leak, 2012; Pot et al., 2018). Managers should be conscious of approaches that discuss different investment selection scenarios to improve the utility's AM. It is sometimes beneficial to adopt decision support tools that do not recommend a single choice to managers but assess and compare investment alternatives for each infrastructure, evaluating the cost and water supply risk (Fletcher et al., 2017).

There is a wide variety of studies related to the replacement and rehabilitation of water infrastructure and methodologies for planning long-term investments in water industry assets (Darmasseelane, 2024). These studies can be grouped into two categories. The first category bases the decision-making on performance indicators and criteria that assess the assets' current condition and the network's efficiency. The second category proposes optimisation approaches to determine the best time to replace an asset.

Regarding the first category, it is crucial to establish appropriate indicators and criteria that show the performance of water utilities in maintaining their infrastructures at acceptable operational levels, their degradation risk and the maturity of AM practices (Vilarinho et al., 2023b). Risk assessment and decision support methodology allow the operator to evaluate the impacts of rehabilitation investments on the risk of exceeding a given failure rate value and to predict the consequences of delaying rehabilitation in terms of costs (Cantos and Juran, 2019). Analysing indicators to assess the assets' life cycle allows the managers to plan long-term investments in the water industry (Ramos-Salgado et al., 2022). One example is the long-term analysis of the Infrastructure Value Index (IVI), which calculates the current replacement costs of assets and establishes their useful life. These methodologies are based on the efficiency of annual capital expenditure and asset deactivation (Alegre et al., 2014; Vieira et al., 2020).

Some authors consider several criteria in their decision-making to study WDS efficiency. Baur et al. (2003) proposed a multi-criteria decision support tool to define strategies for selecting projects to include in the annual rehabilitation plan for a drinking water network. Based in European countries, through detailed cost functions, they defined criteria that affect economic costs and benefits, system reliability, and risk reduction, and they presented each criterion. Some studies suggest multi-criteria models using the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) to select the best rehabilitation projects. The main criticalities that assess the condition and efficiency of water infrastructures are defined, which facilitate the ranking of investments to identify priorities and allocate resources efficiently (Macchiaroli et al., 2023). The analytic network process (ANP) is used in some approaches as it overcomes this limitation. In addition to optimising the design and location of the investment needed to meet the service criteria, it also explains the interdependent relationships between the decision levels and attributes (Grimaldi et al., 2017).

The second category focuses on optimisation approaches developed by water industry researchers. These studies define the ideal replacement time for infrastructure and allow the prioritisation of investments. Most of the time, the approaches minimise the total costs borne by the utility through the failure probability and risk functions associated with different interruption orders (Mailhot et al., 2003; Hong et al., 2006). Other approaches minimise the cost of managing a WDS by defining an optimal variation interval for a given indicator, which portrays the efficiency of the network assets (Vilarinho et al., 2023a). In addition,

some models reflect the benefits of scale economies by grouping the renewal of connected assets (Rokstad and Ugarelli, 2015).

Water utility managers are constantly concerned with optimising expansion costs. However, they must also pay attention to water use and operating costs, given water availability, demand and infrastructure capacity (Fraga et al., 2017). Spatio-temporal variations in demand must be considered when planning investments, and the tools adopted must decide the water volume allocated to each infrastructure (Ahn and Kang, 2014).

Given all these objectives for optimising and prioritising investments, some authors also use multi-objective approaches. These approaches present several objectives and seek to make a trade-off between various factors such as minimising costs, reducing failure risk and water leaks, and decreasing the number of interruptions in the WDS (Dandy and Engelhardt, 2006; Mann and Frey, 2011; Ricalde et al., 2022).

3. Problem formulation

This paper contributes to the decision-making in a capital-intensive industry to simplify the allocation of the capital available for investment by the utility departments. This tool will support informed policy decisions and distribute investments over time according to the utility's available resources.

For this, we developed three optimisation models that return the investments that should be made each year of the planning horizon considered. When the investment is realised, a value classification is created for each investment proposal. The investment proposals may belong to different investment groups (e.g., assets, technology), and each group suggests different criteria and components for determining and quantifying the value that the investment will add to the utility. Various constraints guarantee the proper functioning of the utility's infrastructure and the quality of service provided to customers. Note that some investments are mandatory by legal obligation or due to the utility's concession contract, which means they have to be carried out within the planning horizon of the problem.

The strategy is structured on three study levels. First, Study I maximises the value creation (Section 3.1). Next, Study II minimises the annual budget needed to create a specific value (Section 3.2). Lastly, Study III combines the optimisation objectives of Study I and Study II, using a multi-objective approach (Section 3.3). Appendix details the formulation of the optimisation models proposed in each of these studies.

3.1. Study I: Maximisation of value creation

Study I maximises the total value created by performing the investment proposals. Consider a set of years defining the problem planning horizon, a set of investment groups, and a set of investment proposals for each group.

The model has a binary decision variable ($x_{w,t,i}$), which indicates whether the investment proposal i belonging to group w is realised in year t of the planning horizon. Fig. 1 illustrates the problem formulation of this study and presents its main parameters.

The model constraints ensure that each investment proposal is realised at most once over the planning horizon and that all mandatory investments are performed in the planned period. On an economic level, the model guarantees that the budget invested each year does not exceed the utility's available budget. It also balances the amount financed to each investment group over all years. Regarding the assets' condition, the constraints monitor the average values of the performance and failure risk of the non-invested assets at the end of each year of the planning horizon. Furthermore, the model establishes a maximum value for the likelihood of asset failure. If any asset exceeds this maximum limit, the investment in that asset must be made.

Fig. 1. Problem framework of Study I.

Moreover, the model considers the possibility that some investment proposals must be carried out over the same planning horizon. It is fundamental to analyse each case study individually and understand if this situation occurs. For example, suppose the utility in the water sector wants to invest in the rehabilitation and expansion of a pumping station. In that case, making these two investments in the same planning horizon might be more economically advantageous.

3.2. Study II: Minimisation of the budget required

Similarly to Study I, Study II defines which investments must be realised in each year of the planning horizon using the binary decision variable $x_{w,t,i}$. However, by performing the investment proposals, this new formulation minimises the budget required to create a given value over the planning horizon. The optimisation model determines the annual investment budget. Note that all assumptions of Study II are the same as those of Study I.

3.3. Study III: Multi-objective optimisation

The two optimisation models presented in the previous subsections produce optimal plans that maximise value creation and minimise the required budget. However, the multi-objective approach enables analysis of the two objective functions in a single model. In this new way of looking at the problem, we consider that we have a compromise relationship between the functions, in which improving one implies worsening the other. Unlike single-objective optimisation, which seeks to find a single optimal solution, multi-objective optimisation obtains a set of solutions that balance the conflicting objectives.

To solve the multi-objective problem, we proposed a genetic algorithm (GA) based on the Nondominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) (Deb et al., 2002). The literature suggests that GAs tackle multi-objective optimisation problems better than alternative search strategies (Toro et al., 2006), and NSGA-II is recognised as a state-of-the-art algorithm for such applications. Appendix A.4 provides a general overview, further elaborating on the algorithm's implementation.

4. Case study

To validate the optimisation framework described in Section 3, we consider a Portuguese water utility's investment plan as a case study: *Águas do Douro e Paiva, S.A.* (AdDP). Each utility department presents to the management board the capital investments (CAPEX) they plan to carry out, such as investments in innovation, expansion, replacement

Table 1

Value components considered in the computation of the parameter V_{asset} .

Objective	Components	Description
Assess the current state of the asset	A	Failure risk level
	B	Remaining Useful Life
	C	Recorded failures
Assess the advantages of the investment	D	Technological innovation
	E	Energy efficiency/production
	F	Increase in supply reliability
	G	Reduction of water losses
	H	Economic

and rehabilitation. The board is responsible for allocating the budget to each department. However, AdDP has a limited budget, so managers need to prioritise their budget and optimise their investment plan in an informed approach, ensuring the quality and efficiency of the service provided to consumers.

This chapter applies the models to the case study under analysis. The investments were grouped into two categories: investments in assets and technological investments. Each investment group has different value components, which were defined through expert elicitation based on the utility's organisational objectives and mission: "to manage the upstream water supply system, ensuring efficiency, reliability, quality of service, product safety, and respect for the highest social and environmental values" (AdDP, 2024). Sections 4.1 and 4.2 present the calculations to obtain the value classification of an investment in both categories. Next, in Section 4.3, we implement the formulations for the AdDP case study, determining each of the input parameters of the optimisation models.

4.1. Characterisation of the value of investments in assets

The value classification of each asset investment is obtained based on a set of criteria, considering the asset's current state and the advantages that this investment will bring to the organisation. Table 1 describes the value components considered in this classification, defined by AdDP experts.

The parameter V_{asset} represents the value an investment in an asset generates for the utility and is determined using Eq. (4.1). Experts from AdDP's asset management and engineering department defined the relative weights of each value component. Therefore, the current state of the asset is assessed by three components: failure risk level (A), remaining useful life (B), and failure record of the last four years (C), with a weight of 20%, 15% and 15%, respectively. Regarding each investment's advantages to the utility, the experts established that these five advantages (components D, E, F, G, and H) present the same importance with a relative weight of 10%.

$$V_{asset} = 0.2A + 0.15[B + C] + 0.1[D + E + F + G + H] \quad (4.1)$$

However, some investment proposals aim at the utility's expansion, requiring investments in new assets, such as installing new pipelines to supply a new region. Thus, the value classification of investment proposals in future assets only considers the advantages these investments will return to the organisation if implemented. Since these new assets still need to be built and have yet to be designed, it makes no sense to assess their current state. The AdDP defined that all advantages have the same importance, that is, the same weight in calculating the value classification. This way, Eq. (4.1) can be reduced to Eq. (4.2).

$$V_{asset} = 0.2[D + E + F + G + H] \quad (4.2)$$

Next, we explain how to determine the components A, B, C, D, E, F, G, and H.

Functionality	1	5	10	15	20	25
	2	4	8	12	16	20
	3	3	6	9	12	15
	4	2	4	6	8	10
	5	1	2	3	4	5
		1	2	3	4	5
		Criticality				

Fig. 2. Risk matrix adopted for the classification of assets' risk .

Risk

According to ISO 31000, the risk is the effect of uncertainty on achieving the utility's objectives. Its management supports decision-makers in their informed choice and prioritising actions and contributes to the efficiency of operations and consistent and reliable results. In this way, analysing risk involves studying its causes, origins, consequences, and the likelihood of these consequences happening (ISO, 2009a). Consequently, the level of risk is often expressed through a matrix combining the consequences of a given event and its likelihood of occurrence (ISO, 2009b).

Many authors adopted a risk matrix in their studies and established categories by risk levels (Ostfeld, 2012; Leitão et al., 2013; Pollard, 2016; Cantos and Juran, 2019). In addition, risk scoring systems can rank the failure risk of assets, defining the risk as the product of the likelihood of failure and the consequences of its occurrence (Mann and Frey, 2011). Based on the knowledge of operators and experts, each utility should decide the most relevant factors to be included in the risk classification, attributing some subjectivity to the risk score established.

Fig. 2 presents the risk matrix adopted by AdDP after discussion and agreement among the interested stakeholders. The shaded areas of the matrix represent three levels of risk: low or acceptable (unshaded), moderate or tolerable (grey shading), and high or unacceptable (dark shading). Therefore, the combination of the functionality and criticality of each asset determines its risk level and, consequently, defines component A.

AdDP defines functionality as the likelihood of a failure occurring in the asset, and it is determined taking into account several indicators: the inspection note, the degree of asset obsolescence, the use level of the installed capacity, the number and severity of anomalies and the suitability for operation. On the other hand, criticality reflects the consequences of this failure, which depends on the asset type and the negative impact its failure will have on the utility's water distribution system.

According to the risk matrix in Fig. 2, an asset can present different risk values ($A \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 15, 16, 20, 25\}$). For this reason, since the value classification of an investment proposal in an asset is a weighted average, we define the parameter V_{asset} on a continuous scale, where the highest value that an investment in an asset can bring to the organisation is the value twenty-five ($V_{asset} \in [0, 25]$).

Remaining useful life

The asset's remaining useful life (RUL) is the period from the current time to the end of the asset's useful life. This indicator characterises the asset's health prognosis and is determined based on the estimated performance. Performance is characterised according to the asset's reliability and availability, meaning that RUL generally decreases over time (Lei et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2019).

Fig. 3 illustrates an asset's performance over time, where RUL is the time remaining before the asset's health states cross a failure threshold (FT). In this case study, we used the technical useful life recommended by experts, represented by the parameter $L_{technical}$, to determine the FT of each asset. The parameters RUL and $L_{technical}$ are expressed in years.

Fig. 3. Calculation of the asset's RUL.

Table 2

Recommended technical useful life of the components of a water supply system, expressed in years (Covas et al., 2018).

(a) Civil construction	
Infrastructure	Estimate
Buildings (general)	60
Reservoirs	60
Pumping stations	60
Treatment plants	60
Pipelines (general)	50
Ductile iron, Steel, Stoneware	60
Concrete, Polyethylene	50
Cement, PVC	40
(b) Equipment	
Component type	Estimate
Electromechanical	25
Valves	25
Electrical installations	15
Measuring and control	15
Treatment	15

The Eq. (4.3) calculates the RUL (in years) of an asset considering the year of construction ($Y_{construction}$) and the respective period of the recommended technical useful life ($L_{technical}$). If the asset has been rehabilitated, the year of rehabilitation is considered instead of the year of construction. The parameter $Y_{current}$ corresponds to the current year.

$$RUL = (Y_{construction} + L_{technical}) - Y_{current} \tag{4.3}$$

Each investment proposal is associated with a specific asset. Consequently, each investment proposal's recommended technical useful life depends on the type and nature of the asset with which it is associated. According to the technical guide 23 from the Portuguese regulatory agency (ERSAR), are recommended values for the technical useful life of water supply system assets, which change if the investment proposal refers to the civil construction of the asset or its equipment (Covas et al., 2018). These values are listed in Table 2 (in years).

If the asset's RUL results in a negative value, it indicates it has already been rehabilitated or replaced. In this case, the component B takes its maximum value. Otherwise, we determine component B by using Eq. (4.4). Similar to the scale of the value classification of asset investments, the component $B \in [0, 25]$.

$$B = 25 \times \frac{L_{technical} - RUL}{L_{technical}} \tag{4.4}$$

Failure record

According to the database in the organisation's maintenance software, the failure number of each asset was recorded between April

Table 3
Value components considered in the computation of the parameter $V_{\text{technological}}$.

Components	Description
I	New investment proposal
J	Obsolete technology process or asset
K	Economic advantages
L	Technological renewal
M	Technological innovation
N	process automation
O	Digital transformation

2017 and February 2021. These failures consider work orders for extra maintenance services, corrective maintenance, improvement maintenance, or new works. The breakdowns were separated into civil construction and equipment.

The highest value of failures among all assets was defined to determine the failure classification of an asset associated with civil construction (parameter a) and equipment (parameter b). The parameters N_{cc} and N_{eq} correspond to the total number of asset failures associated with civil construction and equipment, respectively.

We determine the component C , which corresponds to the classification of failures, using the Eqs. (4.5) for civil construction of the asset C_{cc} and (4.6) for equipment C_{eq} . Similar to the scale for the value classification of asset investments, $C \in [0, 25]$.

$$C_{cc} = 25 \times \frac{N_{cc}}{a} \quad (4.5)$$

$$C_{eq} = 25 \times \frac{N_{eq}}{b} \quad (4.6)$$

Advantages of the investment

When an investment is realised, it is expected to bring advantages to the organisation in economic, environmental, and social terms, as well as a better quality of the service provided.

For investment proposals, the organisation will assess whether the realisation of each of these proposals will bring any of the following benefits: (D) modernisation or technological innovation, (E) increased energy efficiency or energy production, (F) improved reliability of supply, (G) reduced water losses or leakages, and (H) economic advantages.

This study defines only two possible situations for each component: D , E , F , G , and H . If the realisation of investment brings one of these five advantages, the respective component takes the value of twenty-five; otherwise, it has a null value - $D, E, F, G, H \in \{0, 25\}$.

4.2. Characterisation of value for technological investments

Most technological investments are associated with the organisation's intangible assets from the Information Systems and Technologies department. Thus, we considered several factors to study the value that technological investments will bring to the organisation. Table 3 describes the seven value components assessed and reflected in the value classification of technological investments.

AdDP experts defined different weights for each component according to the importance and the value the utility attributes to each: 10% if it is something new for the utility, 10% if the technological process/asset is obsolete, 10% for the economic advantages, 17.5% for technological renewal (for example, when an organisation chooses to regularly update or replace some of its technological assets instead of using them until they stop performing their function), 17.5% for technological innovation, 17.5% for process automation (i.e., automating a system or software to streamline the process) and 17.5% for digital transformation. This way, Eq. (4.7) calculates the value classification of technological investments $V_{\text{technological}}$.

$$V_{\text{technological}} = 0.1[I + K + N] + 0.175[J + L + M + O] \quad (4.7)$$

Table 4
Scale of the asset performance classification (AdDP, 2019).

Qualitative scale	Quantitative scale	
	Upper bound	Lower bound
Excellent	5.00	4.50
Good	4.49	3.75
Satisfactory	3.74	3.00
Mediocre	2.99	2.24
Critical	2.23	1.00

The value classification of technological investments is set on the scale $V_{\text{technological}} \in [0, 25]$. In addition, we define two possible situations for the components I , J , K , L , M , N , and O : these components take on the value of twenty-five when the respective criterion is satisfied; otherwise, they have a null value - $I, J, K, L, M, N, O \in \{0, 25\}$.

4.3. Parameter characterisation

After quantifying the value the investments will bring to the Portuguese water utility AdDP, we adjust the formulations developed in Section 3 to the case study of this utility.

The proposed optimisation models comprise several parameters, described in Table A.9 of Appendix A.1. Some of these parameters define the utility's strategic objectives: the available budget and the total value to be created. Others characterise the investment proposals: the price, the mandatory character and the value created by the investment. In addition, specific parameters reflect the condition of the assets associated with the investment proposals: the failure risk, the performance and the likelihood of asset failure.

Furthermore, the models contain reference parameters (e.g., reference parameters for minimum asset performance) that must be defined primarily by AdDP experts to fulfil the requirements imposed by the regulator. The conditions established for this case study are identified below. Table A.10 of Appendix A.1 summarises the value assumed by these reference parameters for each investment group, i.e. investments in assets and technological investments.

Budget constraints

The models balance the amount used annually to realise the investment proposals for each investment group. For asset investments, there is no constraint on the maximum annual budget. On the other hand, for the technological investments group, the total amount, in euros, of the investments made in each year can be at most 35% of the total budget available to invest in that year. This parameter will be defined in Section 5.1 after analysing the investment plan provided by AdDP.

Performance classification

Table 4 shows the qualitative and quantitative scale of the asset performance classification, represented by the parameter $p_{w,i}$ (see Nomenclature in Appendix A.1) and assumes the range of values 1 to 5 (AdDP, 2019). Asset performance is considered acceptable when classified as excellent, good and satisfactory. In contrast, the AdDP assumes performance is unacceptable when mediocre and critical. In this sense, the utility requires that the average performance of assets associated with investment proposals not realised by the end of each year cannot be smaller than three. Only proposals for asset investments hold a performance classification. Thus, this constraint does not apply to the technological investments group.

Failure risk classification

In addition to the performance classification, the asset investment proposals hold a failure risk classification. AdDP classifies the failure risk of assets based on the risk matrix represented in Fig. 2 of Section 4.1. The utility defined that the average failure risk of assets associated with investment proposals not realised by the end of each year cannot be greater than seven. Technology investments also do not have a failure risk classification.

Fig. 4. Annual budget distribution used in the accomplishment of investments in assets (N_1) and technological investments (N_2), according to AdDP's current plan.

Functionality classification

The models present a constraint related to the failure risk of the assets. According to Section 4.1, the functionality corresponds to the likelihood of asset failure, classified by the utility on a scale of 1 to 5.

Therefore, AdDP established that all investment proposals associated with assets with functionality equal to or greater than 4.5 are mandatory to realise in one of the years of the planning horizon. In other words, the maximum acceptable limit for the functionality is 4.5.

Financial stability

Finally, when the utility minimises the budget required, it is necessary a constraint to ensure that the annual budget to invest in each year of the planning horizon should be within a deviation range of $\pm\sigma$ of the average annual budget.

After testing the model several times, the parameter σ was determined with the utility instructions. We assigned different values to σ , and the utility observed the distribution of investments over the planning horizon. Thus, AdDP defined this parameter to allow the organisation to elaborate a stable financial plan by setting a deviation of 10%.

5. Data analysis and results

The utility provided the investment plan for 2022 to 2031. Thus, Section 5.1 shows a detailed analysis of the budget and the value created if AdDP follows the current investment plan. Next, Section 5.2 presents the results obtained when we implement the formulations to AdDP's current investment plan for Studies I, II and III. Finally, we addressed the practical implications of the three approaches for the utility's investment planning and asset management.

We have defined N_w to represent the set of investment proposals of group w (see Nomenclature in Appendix A.1). Thus, the discussion of results tracks three different datasets: the set of proposals from the asset investment group (N_1), the set of proposals from the technological investment group (N_2), and the set of all investment proposals ($N_T : N_1 \cup N_2$). Moreover, the data analysis will be performed only in relative values to ensure the confidentiality of the utility's data.

5.1. Investment plan proposed by addp

Regarding economic costs, Fig. 4 shows the annual budget distribution used in accomplishing the asset investment proposals (set N_1) and the technological investment proposals (set N_2) present in AdDP's current investment plan.

Over the next decade, the proportion of the budget P used in realising the investments in sets N_1 and N_2 will be approximately $0.65P$ and $0.35P$, respectively. For this reason, we define that the amount used annually to implement technological investments cannot exceed 35% of the total available budget.

Table 5

Value created in the next five years by each set, according to AdDP's current investment plan.

	Set N_T	Set N_1	Set N_2
Budget	B_{N_T}	B_{N_1}	B_{N_2}
Created value	$0.73V_{N_T}$	$0.76V_{N_1}$	$0.69V_{N_2}$

Furthermore, in the first five years, it is expected that approximately $0.45P$ will be used in investments in set N_1 and $0.21P$ in investments in set N_2 . Therefore, most of the budget P will be used in the next five years, approximately 66%.

Afterwards, we determined the value created each year of AdDP's current investment plan (from 2022 to 2031). Fig. 5 presents the analysis for the three sets. Consider parameters V_{N_T} , V_{N_1} , and V_{N_2} corresponding to the total value created if AdDP realises all the planned investment proposals regarding sets N_T , N_1 and N_2 , respectively ($V_{N_T} = V_{N_1} + V_{N_2}$). We calculated the value created by each investment proposal based on the criteria defined in Sections 4.1 and 4.2.

According to Fig. 5, if AdDP complies with its current investment plan for the next five years, the realisation of the investment proposals of sets N_T , N_1 and N_2 will create approximately $0.73V_{N_T}$, $0.76V_{N_1}$, and $0.69V_{N_2}$, respectively. These data are summarised in Table 5.

Let B_{N_T} , B_{N_1} , and B_{N_2} represent the total budget expected to be invested in the next five years, according to AdDP's current investment plan, for sets N_T , N_1 and N_2 , respectively ($B_{N_T} = B_{N_1} + B_{N_2}$).

5.2. Investment plan recommendations

Every five years, AdDP's investment plan must be revisited, and afterwards, it must be approved by the sector regulator within the Study of Economic and Financial Feasibility. This study allows for determining the necessary tariff to be applied to users for the supply activity. Therefore, we defined a planning horizon of five years to implement the formulations developed from 2022 to 2026.

Sections 5.2.1–5.2.3 present the results obtained with optimisation models of Studies I, II and III, respectively. After analysing the investment plan, we found a group of investment proposals in assets that must be realised in the same planning horizon. These investments are related to the supply and installation of solar photovoltaic equipment. When one of these is performed in a specific infrastructure over the planning horizon, other similar investments must also be made.

5.2.1. Study I

Study I maximises the value creation in the next five years by realising the investment proposals. We analyse the results obtained using the budget planned to invest in the next five years, according to AdDP's current investment plan, that is, using the budget B_{N_T} , B_{N_1} , and B_{N_2} for the set N_T , N_1 , and N_2 , respectively.

Fig. 5. Value created in each year of the planning horizon of AdDP’s current investment plan for each set.

Fig. 6. Relation between the value created for the utility by realising the investments of sets N_T and N_1 and the available budget (Study I).

Regarding the set of investments in assets and technological investments (N_T), we verify that $0.82V_{N_T}$ will be created using budget B_{N_T} . According to the AdDP investment plan, the N_T investment proposals will create $0.73V_T$, a 12.3% increase in the value created. Regarding the set of asset investments (N_1), we conclude that $0.91V_{N_1}$ will be created using budget B_{N_1} . According to the AdDP investment plan, the N_1 investment proposals will create $0.76V_{N_1}$, a 19.7% increase in the value created.

Subsequently, we analyse the values V_{N_T} and V_{N_1} created from the variation of the budget B_{N_T} and B_{N_1} available for sets N_T and N_1 , respectively. This relation is represented in Fig. 6. For both sets, we observed that the value created increases linearly with the increased available budget.

Finally, we assessed the results concerning the technological investments (N_2). If the utility provides the budget B_{N_2} for the next five years, $0.70V_{N_2}$ will be created. As the realisation of the investment proposals of set N_2 according to the AdDP investment plan will create $0.69V_{N_2}$, the percentage increase in value created for the organisation was only 1.4%, compared to AdDP’s current investment plan. Most technology investments have a high-value rating and require high-value investment (unlike asset investments). Moreover, many of these investments are mandatory, which can limit the scope for optimising and improving value creation.

Afterwards, we performed a sensitivity analysis by assigning different values to the budget B_{N_2} available in the next five years, and we analysed the value V_{N_2} created by realising investments in set N_2 . In Fig. 7, we verified that the increased budget available B_{N_2} incurs an increase in the value V_{N_2} created for the organisation. Furthermore,

Fig. 7. Relation between the value created for the utility by realising the investments of set N_2 and the available budget (Study I).

we observed that value creation grows faster until a budget of $0.87B_{N_2}$. After this budget, the value created declines and stabilises.

Study I prioritises investments of lower financial value. Thus, as the total budget available increases, most of the investments that are not chosen require high budgets, which makes their realisation harder. This evidence is more notorious in technological investments. It explains why the value created is approximately constant in the range $[0.94B_{N_2}, B_{N_2}]$.

Table 6 summarises the results obtained for each set and compares them when implementing Study I and using AdDP’s current investment plan.

After analysing the results obtained from Study I, we conclude that the increase in value created in the case of asset and technological

Fig. 8. Relation between the budget used by the utility to realise the investments of sets N_T and N_1 and the minimum value that needs to be created (Study II).

Table 6
Results obtained with the Study I.

Set	Budget	Created value	
		AdDP's current plan	Study I
N_T	B_{N_T}	$73\%V_{N_T}$	$82\%V_{N_T}$
N_1	B_{N_1}	$76\%V_{N_1}$	$91\%V_{N_1}$
N_2	B_{N_2}	$69\%V_{N_2}$	$70\%V_{N_2}$

Table 7
Results obtained with the Study II.

Set	Created value	Budget	
		AdDP's current plan	Study II
N_T	$73\%V_{N_T}$	B_{N_T}	$77\%B_{N_T}$
N_1	$76\%V_{N_1}$	B_{N_1}	$69\%B_{N_1}$
N_2	$69\%V_{N_2}$	B_{N_2}	$94\%B_{N_2}$

investments (N_T) results mainly from the optimisation performed on the set of asset investments (N_1). Most technology investments must be made continuously and are driven by mandates, which constrains optimisation.

5.2.2. Study II

Study II minimises the budget required to create a given value for the organisation in a planning horizon of five years, i.e., to create v^{total} (see Table A.9 in Appendix A.1). In these results, we intended to produce the same value as in AdDP's current investment plan, that is, $0.73V_{N_T}$, $0.76V_{N_1}$ and $0.69V_{N_2}$ with the realisation of the investments of sets N_T , N_1 and N_2 , respectively.

Firstly, we studied the budget B_{N_T} and B_{N_1} AdDP for different values v^{total} . In other words, we varied the value V_{N_T} and V_{N_1} that we want to create, at least, over the next five years by making the investments of sets N_T and N_1 , respectively. This relation is shown in Fig. 8.

Through the analysis of Fig. 8, we found that to create $0.73V_{N_T}$ (realisation of asset and technological investments - N_T), the budget required is $0.77B_{N_T}$. In other words, it is possible to reduce approximately $0.23B_{N_T}$ compared with AdDP's current investment plan. Furthermore, regarding the set of asset investments (N_1), we verified that it uses the budget $0.69B_{N_1}$ to create $0.76V_{N_1}$. That is, we observed a budget reduction of 31%.

Next, we analysed the technological investment set (N_2). Thus, Fig. 9 shows the relationship between the budget B_{N_2} used by AdDP for different values V_{N_2} that it aims to create, at a minimum, over the next five years. Interpreting the data from this Figure, we observed that it requires the budget $0.94B_{N_2}$ to create $0.69V_{N_2}$. Therefore, there is a budget reduction of only 6%.

Figs. 8 and 9 show that the budget required decreases when we decrease the value we want to create in all three sets. However, no matter how great the increase in the constraint slack that limits the parameter v^{total} , the budget that needs to be used remains constant. It happens because the optimisation model has to comply with all the

other constraints and, for this, it needs to invest at least $0.40B_{N_T}$, $0.29B_{N_1}$ and $0.44B_{N_2}$ for the sets N_T , N_1 and N_2 , respectively.

Table 7 presents the results from Study II and the results according to AdDP's current investment plan for each set. We verified that the budget needed to create the same value as AdDP's current plan is significantly smaller in Study II than in AdDP's current investment plan. However, when comparing the values obtained in the three sets, we noticed that the reduction in the budget is higher in the asset investment set (N_1). Consequently, we concluded that the budget reduction in set N_T results from the influence of set N_1 , as observed in Study I.

5.2.3. Study III

Study III considers a five-year planning horizon following Studies I and II. This new approach analyses the two conflicting objective functions in multi-objective optimisation: maximise the value creation (f_1) and minimise the budget used (f_2). We considered the budget B_{N_T} , B_{N_1} and B_{N_2} as the amount available to invest over the next five years for sets N_T , N_1 , and N_2 , respectively. In addition, we also define that:

$$v^{total} \geq 0.50V_{N_T} \text{ for } N_T$$

$$v^{total} \geq 0.50V_{N_1} \text{ for } N_1$$

$$v^{total} \geq 0.50V_{N_2} \text{ for } N_2$$

Note that V_{N_T} , V_{N_1} , and V_{N_2} correspond to the total value created if AdDP realises all the planned investment proposals in 2022–2031.

The GA failed to generate feasible solutions for the parameters used on the single-objective problems. Therefore, the constraints were relaxed through parameter modifications to address this challenge. New values of deviation range ($\sigma = 0.2$) and average failure risk ($r_1^{max} = 8$) were considered to obtain non-dominated solutions (Pareto front).

Regarding the GA parameters, the size of the population TP and the number of generations G were empirically defined respectively as 200 and 100. The parameter $M1$ was defined empirically as 10^2 for set N_T , and 10 for sets N_1 and N_2 . For $M2$, 10^6 was used for all sets.

Given the stochastic nature of GA, 20 rounds of tests were executed for each set using the parameters described previously. The

Fig. 9. Relation between the budget used by the utility to realise the investments of the set N_2 and the minimum value that needs to be created (Study II).

Fig. 10. Optimal results of Study I and Study II models and alternative solutions from multi-objective optimisation.

average computational time for set N_1 was 40.0238 min, for N_2 was 14.2035 min, and for N_T was 47.3201 min. We selected a non-dominated frontier from one of the rounds for each set to analyse the results. The corresponding results are presented in Fig. 10. Fig. 10 also presents the trade-off between the objectives of the optimisation models from Study I and Study II for the three sets. We observed the optimal solutions for each binary linear programming model, considering the new problem conditions ($\sigma = 0.2$ and $r_1^{max} = 8$). The non-dominated solutions represent the alternative solutions found by the multi-objective model. We verified that by improving objective f_1 , we penalised objective f_2 ; the opposite is also true. These solutions are given to managers, so they have different possibilities in their decision-making. This way, they can implement the solution that presents the investment plan best suited to the utility's strategic objectives.

Even though GA could not generate all solutions close to the optimal solution of Study I for set N_T (Fig. 10(a)), the result obtained is already considered satisfactory by the utility as it generates alternative solutions close to 60% of V_{N_T} and B_{N_T} .

Table 8 summarises the results of three alternative solutions from multi-objective optimisation for each set. We analyse the solution closest to the objective f_1 and the other closest to the objective f_2 (alternative solutions A and C, respectively). We also studied one of the alternative solutions that best balances these two objectives (alternative solution B).

This analysis compares the alternative solutions analysed to AdDP's current investment plan. According to the utility's plan, it will create $0.73V_{N_T}$, $0.76V_{N_1}$ and $0.69V_{N_2}$ over the next five years, for sets N_T , N_1 , and N_2 , respectively.

As for the budget used, all the alternative solutions obtained resulted in a significant reduction. Regarding value creation, we observed that the alternative solution for set N_T that best maximises the value created (solution C) only creates $0.65V_{N_T}$, representing a decrease of 12%. The same happens with set N_2 , where alternative solution C creates $0.69V_{N_2}$. That is, we noticed a reduction of 1%. On the other

hand, alternative solution B of set N_1 allows an increase of 1% in the value created with a budget reduction of 30%. We concluded that all the alternative solutions found between 77% V_{N_1} and 88% V_{N_1} (solution C) represent near-optimal solutions. They simultaneously lead to an increase in the value created and a decrease in the budget required compared to AdDP's current investment plan.

5.3. Policy implications

The proposed methods are transparent because they guide well-founded policy decisions for the utility community and stakeholders. This goal is achieved by optimising and prioritising investments using clear criteria. The formulations allow managers to simplify the process of planning long-term investments. They help to ensure the WDS's normal functioning, monitor the failure risk of water infrastructures, and establish the optimum time for realising each investment. In addition, they excel in the conscious allocation of capital by the utility's departments.

The results provide management policies balancing the distribution of investments over the planning horizon and avoiding significant discrepancies in the budget used. Managers can draw up a stable financial plan, facilitating the fulfilment of all the planned investments. Furthermore, this planning substantially impacts mobilising human resources. A solid financial plan makes it possible to spread tasks among the utility's operators better, decreasing the need for hiring or firing during the period.

Looking closely at each study, if the utility manager has only one goal to meet, the models proposed in Study I and Study II can find the best solution to implement. When managers desire to consider both objectives, the Study III approach makes a compromise and emerges as a good alternative. The multi-objective approach finds solutions to implement by optimising the two conflicting objectives simultaneously, depending on the adversities faced, such as economic limitations and the strategies defined. In this way, managers have multiple quality

Table 8
Details of some alternative solutions from multi-objective optimisation.

Set	Alternative solution	Study III		Variation from AdDP's current plan	
		Value created	Budget	Value created	Budget used
N_T	A	$52\%V_{N_T}$	$47\%B_{N_T}$	$-29\%V_{N_T}$	$-53\%B_{N_T}$
	B	$57\%V_{N_T}$	$54\%B_{N_T}$	$-22\%V_{N_T}$	$-46\%B_{N_T}$
	C	$65\%V_{N_T}$	$65\%B_{N_T}$	$-12\%V_{N_T}$	$-35\%B_{N_T}$
N_1	A	$53\%V_{N_1}$	$47\%B_{N_1}$	$-30\%V_{N_1}$	$-53\%B_{N_1}$
	B	$77\%V_{N_1}$	$70\%B_{N_1}$	$1\%V_{N_1}$	$-30\%B_{N_1}$
	C	$88\%V_{N_1}$	$93\%B_{N_1}$	$15\%V_{N_1}$	$-7\%B_{N_1}$
N_2	A	$51\%V_{N_2}$	$54\%B_{N_2}$	$-27\%V_{N_2}$	$-46\%B_{N_2}$
	B	$60\%V_{N_2}$	$70\%B_{N_2}$	$-14\%V_{N_2}$	$-30\%B_{N_2}$
	C	$69\%V_{N_2}$	$94\%B_{N_2}$	$-1\%V_{N_2}$	$-6\%B_{N_2}$

solutions for deciding on investment policies and can choose the most convenient solution for the utility.

In conclusion, the models proposed in this work were approved by a Portuguese water utility, as they have proved to be powerful tools for designing policy decisions. As the national regulatory agency has to validate the investment plan, the optimisation approaches bring several benefits to the water utility. In particular, they help utilities detect anomalies in managing their assets, prioritise critical actions and allow managers to justify their decisions. In addition, they contribute to providing excellent service to communities and efficiently managing the utility's capital expenditure.

6. Conclusion

This work adds an innovative approach to AM in capital-intensive industries by planning long-term investments to the existing literature. The proposed formulations fill the gap in the literature, focusing on the value created when we realise investments and considering the limitations managers face. It covers two optimisation objectives: maximise value creation (Study I) and minimise the budget used (Study II). In addition, we developed a multi-objective model (Study III) to assess the trade-off between these two objectives and generate alternative solutions.

The models presented optimise and prioritise investments and indicate the best time to make them. Any capital-intensive industry can use the formulations by incorporating specific constraints and defining the concept of investment value according to the utility's goals and vision. This work addresses powerful methods that help managers decide and distribute work evenly over the planning horizon. Furthermore, it allows managers to become more aware of capital expenditure, contributing to the utility's financial stability and supporting their choices to stakeholders.

The case study results demonstrate the potential of the formulations, significantly reducing the budget used, boosting value creation, and ensuring proper AM. However, this paper presents some limitations. The value of the indicators that assess the condition of the assets in this horizon has yet to be predicted. Developing a metric to predict the risk of asset failure will be valuable. Moreover, the influence of the inflation rate on the investment budget over the years has yet to be evaluated. Another area for improvement evident in the case study is the imprecise metrics used to evaluate technological investments. Although these metrics prioritise technological investments, they require better optimisation. The work will benefit from developing new indicators for this investment group in the future.

This work focuses on optimising capital investments (CAPEX), which consists of potential processes that water utilities can adopt. As a result, they will help policymakers design better regulatory strategies and ensure the fairness of approving operators' investment plans. Future developments may include operating expenditure (OPEX) through the trade-off between maintenance or repair actions and replacement or rehabilitation investments. It is necessary to deepen the study of the asset's life cycle and analyse all the possibilities for intervention to define the right decision and time.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mariana Casalta: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Flávia Barbosa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Luciana Yamada:** Software, Methodology. **Lígia B. Ramos:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Acknowledgements

The first author acknowledges the financial support provided by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952060.

Appendix. Optimisation models

In order to manage the water utilities' assets and optimise their investment plan, we develop three optimisation models. Below, we detail the nomenclature of the proposed approaches and present the formulation of the three optimisation models.

A.1. Nomenclature

Consider Y , the set of years defining the problem planning horizon, $Y = \{1, \dots, m\}$, C the set of investment groups, $C = \{1, \dots, n\}$, and N_w is the set of investment proposals of group w , where $w \in C$. Additionally, we define two other datasets: A_w , the set of investments in assets that already exist in the organisation and that belong to a given investments group w ($A_w \subset N_w$) and H_s , the set of groups s of investment proposals that must be made over the same planning horizon, $s = \{1, \dots, o\}$.

The three optimisation models present the binary decision variable $x_{w,t,i}$. It takes the value of 1 if investment proposal i of belonging to group w is realised in year t and 0 otherwise. Moreover, we add the auxiliary binary decision variable h_s . It takes the value of 1 if none of the investment proposals belonging to the group s are realised and 0 otherwise.

Table A.9 summarises the parameters used in this work. All values belong to the set of positive real numbers (\mathbb{R}^+). In exception, we define the parameter $q_{w,i}$, which is binary: it takes the value of 1 if the investment proposal i of group w is mandatory to be realised over the planning horizon and 0 otherwise.

Table A.9
Parameters of optimisation models.

Parameter	Description
σ	Investment deviation
β_w	Maximum proportion of the total budget that can be invested in the group w each year t
b_t	Budget, in euros, available to invest in year t
v^{total}	Total value to be created over the planning horizon
$a_{w,i}$	Amount of euros required to realise the investment proposal i from group w
$q_{w,i}$	Indicates if it is mandatory to realise the investment proposal i of the group w over the planning horizon
$v_{w,i}$	Value classification of investment proposal i from group w
$f_{w,i}$	Likelihood of asset failure with investment proposal i from group w
$p_{w,i}$	Asset performance associated with investment proposal i from group w
$r_{w,i}$	Asset failure risk associated with investment proposal i from group w
f_w^{max}	Maximum acceptable likelihood of asset failure for each investment group w
p_w^{min}	Minimum average level of asset performance for each group w
r_w^{max}	Maximum average level of asset risk for each group w

Table A.10
Values assigned to the reference parameters: AdDP case study.

σ	β_2	f_1^{max}	p_1^{min}	r_1^{max}
0.1	0.35	4.5	3	7

Case study

The case study of this work is the investment plan of a Portuguese water utility: *Águas do Douro e Paiva, S.A.* (AdDP). AdDP divided its investment proposals into two groups: investments in assets ($w = 1$) and technological investments ($w = 2$).

As mentioned at the beginning of Section 4.3, some parameters define the utility's strategic objectives (b_t, v^{total}); others characterise the investment proposals ($a_{w,i}, q_{w,i}, v_{w,i}$) and portray the condition of the assets ($f_{w,i}, p_{w,i}, r_{w,i}$). The remaining parameters represent reference values that establish the assumptions of this case study ($\sigma, \beta_w, f_w^{max}, p_w^{min}, r_w^{max}$). Table A.10 presents the values assigned to these parameters for each investment group.

AdDP assumes that technological investments do not present performance, risk of failure and probability of failure classifications. Therefore, the parameters $f_{w,i}, p_{w,i}, r_{w,i}, f_w^{max}, p_w^{min}$, and r_w^{max} do not apply to proposals from the technological investment group ($w = 2$).

A.2. Study I

Study I maximises the total value created by realising the investment proposals. The following binary linear programming model is proposed:

$$\text{Max} \sum_{w \in C} \sum_{t \in Y} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times v_{w,i}) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\text{s.t.} \sum_{i \in Y} x_{w,t,i} \leq 1, \quad \forall w \in C, i \in N_w \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\sum_{w \in C} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times a_{w,i}) \leq b_t, \quad \forall t \in Y \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times a_{w,i}) \leq \beta_w \times b_t, \quad \forall w \in C, t \in Y \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\sum_{i \in Y} x_{w,t,i} \geq q_{w,i}, \quad \forall w \in C, i \in N_w \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$p_w^{min} \left[|A_w| - \sum_{m=1}^t \sum_{i \in A_w} x_{w,m,i} \right] \leq \sum_{i \in A_w} p_{w,i} - \sum_{m=1}^t \sum_{i \in A_w} (x_{w,m,i} \times p_{w,i}), \quad \forall w \in C, t \in Y \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\sum_{i \in A_w} r_{w,i} - \sum_{m=1}^t \sum_{i \in A_w} (x_{w,m,i} \times r_{w,i}) \leq r_w^{max} \left[|A_w| - \sum_{m=1}^t \sum_{i \in A_w} x_{w,m,i} \right], \quad \forall w \in C, t \in Y \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$f_{w,i} - f_w^{max} \leq \sum_{t \in Y} x_{w,t,i} - \varepsilon, \quad \forall w \in C, i \in A_w \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$|H_s| - \sum_{w \in H_s} \sum_{t \in Y} \sum_{i \in H_s} x_{w,t,i} = |H_s| \times h_s, \quad \forall s = \{1, \dots, o\} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$h_s \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall s = \{1, \dots, o\} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$x_{w,t,i} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall w \in C, t \in Y, i \in N_w \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Consider $|A_w|$ and $|H_w|$ the cardinality of set A_w and H_w , respectively. In addition, parameter $\beta_w \in [0, 1]$ and the term ε represents an infinitesimal value. We highlight that only investment proposals in assets already existing in the utility hold values $p_{w,i}$ and $r_{w,i}$. Investment proposals in new assets do not deliver these parameters.

A.3. Study II

Study II minimises the budget needed to create value over the planning horizon by making investment proposals. The following binary linear programming model is proposed:

$$\text{Min} \sum_{w \in C} \sum_{t \in Y} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times a_{w,i}) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\text{s.t.} \sum_{w \in C} \sum_{t \in Y} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times v_{w,i}) \geq v^{total} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$\sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times a_{w,i}) \leq \beta_w \left[\sum_{w' \in C} \sum_{t' \in Y} (x_{w',t',i} \times a_{w',i}) \right], \quad \forall w \in C, t \in Y \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$|Y| \sum_{w \in C} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times a_{w,i}) \geq (1 - \sigma) \left[\sum_{w \in C} \sum_{t' \in Y} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t',i} \times a_{w,i}) \right], \quad \forall t \in Y \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$|Y| \sum_{w \in C} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times a_{w,i}) \leq (1 + \sigma) \left[\sum_{w \in C} \sum_{t' \in Y} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t',i} \times a_{w,i}) \right], \quad \forall t \in Y \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$(\text{A.2}), (\text{A.5}), (\text{A.6}), (\text{A.7}), (\text{A.8}), (\text{A.9}), (\text{A.10}), (\text{A.11})$$

In contrast to Study I, the optimisation model of Study II determines annual investment budget. It means that parameter b_t is no longer an input variable as in Study I. Consequently, the constraint (A.4) in Study I takes into account the available budget b_t , was replaced by the constraint (A.14) in Study II that considers the budget used annually.

Constraints (A.15) and (A.16) indicate that the annual budget used over the planning horizon must be within a deviation range of $\pm\sigma$ of the average annual budget. Consider $|Y|$ the respective cardinality of the set.

A.4. Study III

Study III consists of a multi-objective optimisation model. It maximises value creation and minimises the required budget simultaneously.

To solve this model, we proposed a genetic algorithm (GA) based on the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) (Deb et al., 2002). An initial population of size TP is created considering the feasibility of some constraints. The population is evaluated on the two objective functions: value creation maximisation and budget

Fig. A.11. Binary encoding representing a potential solution k in GA population.

minimisation. A feasibility verification on the remaining constraints is applied, in which infeasible solutions are penalised by a factor.

A parent population of size TP is created with the binary tournament selection process, which randomly selects two individuals from the population, and the best one is selected to integrate the parent population. Afterwards, the crossover is applied to the parent population. Then, to generate variability and more diverse solutions, the mutation creates an offspring population with a $4TP$ size. The mixed population is sorted according to non-domination rank and crowding distance, and the best individuals compose the next population with size TP . After G generations, the algorithm returns the non-dominated frontier, and only the feasible ones are considered the final solution for the problem. TP and G are determined based on what best suits the set. Detailed information on the algorithm is presented in the following subsections.

Coding

A binary representation encodes a solution. An individual k represents an investment plan. In the binary matrix, rows represent years t in the planning horizon, and the columns represent the investments of each group. In the first part of the individual, the investments of the first group are ordered, followed by the investments of the second group. Then, $z_{t,(w,i)}$ identify if, in year t of the planning horizon, the investment i of group w is realised. If realised, a value of 1 is assumed, and 0 otherwise. Fig. A.11 exemplifies an individual for a problem with two groups, where $w = 1$ has nine investment proposals and $w = 2$ five investment proposals.

Initialisation

The initial population is randomly generated and ensures the constraints (A.2), (A.5), (A.8), and (A.9) (Studies I and II).

Evaluation

For each k , two fitness functions are assigned to fit the objective functions f_1 value creation maximisation (A.1) and f_2 budget minimisation (A.12). A feasibility verification evaluates if the individual meets the constraints of each model. In violation cases, the penalty calculates how much the value of the constraint (CV_d) exceeds its boundary (CB_d) for all violated constraints d . Eq. (A.17) represents the penalties for f_1 (for f_2 , the calculation is analogous):

$$PN_{f_1} = \sum_{d \in D} \frac{CV_d}{CB_d} \tag{A.17}$$

Finally, the penalty factor is integrated into each objective function as follows:

$$f_1 = \sum_{w \in C} \sum_{i \in Y} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times v_{w,i}) - M1 \times PN_{f_1} \tag{A.18}$$

$$f_2 = \sum_{w \in C} \sum_{i \in Y} \sum_{i \in N_w} (x_{w,t,i} \times a_{w,i}) + M2 \times PN_{f_2} \tag{A.19}$$

For f_1 , the constraints considered for penalisation are: (A.3), (A.4), (A.6), and (A.7). For f_2 , the constraints considered for penalisation are: (A.6), (A.7), (A.13), (A.14), (A.15), and (A.16). Parameters $M1$ and $M2$

represent values of a particular order of magnitude. The appropriate values must be determined as they significantly influence the objective function.

Crossover

The uniform crossover operator generates a new offspring population that combines the characteristics of the parent population created in a previous step by the binary tournament. Two parents are randomly selected to generate two offspring solutions. Each column of the binary matrix of the offspring, which represents the assignment of the investment proposal, has a 50% chance to come from the first parent and the other 50% from the second parent. A mask is randomly generated with values 0 or 1 to assign what gene will come for each parent.

Mutation

The mutation operator introduces variability in the solution. In addressing the problem, four mutation types were employed, ensuring that the individual complies with the same constraints considered in the initialisation of the population. Each offspring produces four additional solutions by applying each of the following mutation types:

1. Swap year: select two different years randomly from the individual (rows in the binary matrix) and switch the entire annual investment plan between the two chosen years.
2. Swap investment proposals: select two distinct proposals randomly from the individual (columns in the binary matrix). If the assignments are different, swap their corresponding values. If the assignments are the same, randomly choose a new value (0 or 1) and a new year, and change for both investment proposals.
3. Reconstruct annual investment: randomly select an annual investment plan (a row in the binary matrix) and reset all assigned investments to zero.
4. Reconstruct investment proposals: randomly select two proposals (columns in the binary matrix) and reset all values to zero.

Non-dominated sorting approach

The non-dominated sorting approach compares two individuals within the population. This technique is used in the binary tournament and the population selection stage at the end of each generation. Each individual has two attributes based on the non-dominated ranking and the crowding distance (Deb et al., 2002). When comparing two solutions, the best ones are in the lower ranks. Suppose the solutions are located on the same front. In that case, we prioritise the solutions with higher crowding distances, which means that the solution is found in less populated regions and is consequently more diverse.

References

AdDP, 2024. Visão, missão e política de responsabilidade empresarial.
 Ahn, J., Kang, D., 2014. Optimal planning of water supply system for long-term sustainability. *J. Hydro-Environ. Res.* 8, 410–420.
 Alegre, H., Amaral, R., Brito, R., Baptista, J., 2020. Public policies as strategic asset management enablers: the case of Portugal. *H2oj* 3, 428–436.

- Alegre, H., Coelho, S., 2012. Infrastructure asset management of urban water systems. In: *Water Supply System Analysis—Selected Topics*. pp. 49–74.
- Alegre, H., Vitorino, D., Coelho, S., 2014. Infrastructure value index: a powerful modelling tool for combined long-term planning of linear and vertical assets. *Procedia Eng.* 89, 1428–1436.
- Almeida, N., Trindade, M., Komljenovic, D., Finger, M., 2022. A conceptual construct on value for infrastructure asset management. *Util. Policy* 75, 101354.
- Anon, 2015. Institute of asset management asset management-an anatomy. Version 3.
- Anon, 2019. AdDP Avaliação da Condição dos Ativos.
- Anon, 2023. AWWA State of the Water Industry. American Water Works Association.
- Anon, 2024. United nations sustainable development goals. Available in: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>.
- Baur, R., Le Gauffre, P., Sægrov, S., 2003. Multi-criteria decision support for annual rehabilitation programmes in drinking water networks. In: *Water Science and Technology: Water Supply*, vol. 3, pp. 43–50.
- Belay, A., Puranik, S., Gallart-Fernández, R., Tuiskula, H., Melendez, J., Lamprinos, I., Díaz-González, F., Smolnikar, M., 2021. Developing novel technologies and services for intelligent low voltage electricity grids: Cost-benefit analysis and policy implications. *Energies* 15, 94.
- Brunekreeft, G., Rammerstorfer, M., 2021. OPEX-risk as a source of CAPEX-bias in monopoly regulation. *Competition Regul. Netw. Ind.* 22, 20–34.
- Cai, B., Shao, X., Liu, Y., Kong, X., Wang, H., Xu, H., Ge, W., 2019. Remaining useful life estimation of structure systems under the influence of multiple causes: Subsea pipelines as a case study. *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.* 67, 5737–5747.
- Cantos, W., Juran, I., 2019. Infrastructure aging risk assessment for water distribution systems. *Water Supply* 19, 899–907.
- Covas, D., Cabral, M., Pinheiro, A., Marchionni, V., Antunes, S., Lopes, N., Mamouros, L., Brôco, N., 2018. Guia Técnico 23. Custos de Construção de Infraestruturas Associadas ao Ciclo Urbano da Água. Technical Guide 23, Infrastructure Construction Costs Associated with the Urban Water Cycle, IST.
- Dandy, G., Engelhardt, M., 2006. Multi-objective trade-offs between cost and reliability in the replacement of water mains. *J. Water Res. Plan. Manag.* 132, 79–88.
- Darmasseelane, K., 2024. The long-term asset investment planning solution offerings of 14 prominent vendors. Available in: <https://www.verdantix.com/insights/blogs/verdantix-green-quadrant-benchmarks-the-long-term-asset-investment-planning-solution-offerings-of-14-prominent-vendors>.
- Davies, A., 2004. Moving base into high-value integrated solutions: a value stream approach. *Ind. Corp. Change* 13, 727–756.
- Deb, K., Pratap, A., Agarwal, S., Meyarivan, T., 2002. A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.* 6, 182–197.
- El-Akruti, K., Dwight, R., Zhang, T., 2013. The strategic role of engineering asset management. *Int. J. Prod. Econ.* 146, 227–239.
- Ferreira, B., Carriço, N., 2019. Urban water infrastructure asset management plan: Case study. *Open Eng.* 9, 459–467.
- Fletcher, S., Miotti, M., Swaminathan, J., Klemun, M., Strzepak, K., Siddiqi, A., 2017. Water supply infrastructure planning: Decision-making framework to classify multiple uncertainties and evaluate flexible design. *J. Water Resour. Plan. Manag.* 143, 04017061.
- Fraga, C., Medellín-Azuara, J., Marques, G., 2017. Planning for infrastructure capacity expansion of urban water supply portfolios with an integrated simulation-optimization approach. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 29, 247–256.
- Gleick, P., 2018. Transitions to freshwater sustainability. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 115, 8863–8871.
- Goforth, E., Yosri, A., El-Dakhkhni, W., Wiebe, L., 2022. Infrastructure asset management system optimized configuration: A genetic algorithm-complex network theoretic metamanagement approach. *J. Infrastructure Syst.* 28, 04022029.
- González-Prida, V., Guillén, A., Gómez, J., Crespo, A., Fuente, A., 2019. An approach to quantify value provided by an engineered asset according to the ISO 5500x series of standards. In: *Asset Intelligence Through Integration and Interoperability and Contemporary Vibration Engineering Technologies: Proceedings of the 12th World Congress on Engineering Asset Management and the 13th International Conference on Vibration Engineering and Technology of Machinery*. pp. 189–196.
- Grimaldi, M., Pellicchia, V., Fasolino, I., 2017. Urban plan and water infrastructures planning: A methodology based on spatial ANP. *Sustainability* 9, 771.
- Hong, H., Allouche, E., Trivedi, M., 2006. Optimal scheduling of replacement and rehabilitation of water distribution systems. *J. Infrastructure Syst.* 12, 184–191.
- ISO, 2009a. ISO 31000:2009. Risk Management - Principles and Guidelines. International Organization for Standardization.
- ISO, 2009b. ISO/IEC 31010:2009. Risk Management - Risk Assessment Techniques. International Organization for Standardization.
- ISO ISO 55000:2014, 2014. Asset Management - Overview, Principles and Terminology. International Organization for Standardization.
- Kang, H., 2019. Challenges for water infrastructure asset management in South Korea. *Water Policy* 21, 934–944.
- Komljenovic, D., Gaha, M., Abdul-Nour, G., Langheit, C., Bourgeois, M., 2016. Risks of extreme and rare events in asset management. *Saf. Sci.* 88, 129–145.
- Krampe, J., Leak, M., 2012. Strategic planning approach for optimising investment at WWTPs. *Water Pract. Technol.* 7.
- Lei, Y., Li, N., Guo, L., Li, N., Yan, T., Lin, J., 2018. Machinery health prognostics: A systematic review from data acquisition to RUL prediction. *Mech. Syst. Signal Process.* 104, 799–834.
- Leitão, J., Almeida, M., Simões, N., Martins, A., 2013. Methodology for qualitative urban flooding risk assessment. *Water Sci. Technol.* 68, 829–838.
- Lima, E., Costa, A., 2019. Improving asset management under a regulatory view. *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* 190, 106523.
- Macchiaroli, M., Dolores, L., De Mare, G., 2023. Multicriteria decision making and water infrastructure: An application of the analytic hierarchy process for a sustainable ranking of investments. *Appl. Sci.* 13, 8284.
- Mailhot, A., Poulin, A., Villeneuve, J., 2003. Optimal replacement of water pipes. *Water Resour. Res.* 39.
- Maletič, D., Almeida, N., Gomišček, B., Maletič, M., 2022. Understanding motives for and barriers to implementing asset management system: An empirical study for engineered physical assets. *Prod. Plan. Control.*
- Mann, E., Frey, J., 2011. Optimized pipe renewal programs ensure cost-effective asset management. In: *Pipelines 2011: A Sound Conduit for Sharing Solutions*. pp. 44–54.
- Marques, R., Pinto, F., 2018. How to watch the watchmen? The role and measurement of regulatory governance. *Util. Policy* 51, 73–81.
- Ostfeld, A., 2012. *Water Supply System Analysis: Selected Topics*. IntechOpen.
- Pollard, S., 2016. *Risk Management for Water and Wastewater Utilities*. Iwa Publishing.
- Pot, W., Dewulf, A., Biesbroek, G., Vlist, M., Termeer, C., 2018. What makes long-term investment decisions forward looking: A framework applied to the case of Amsterdam's new sea lock. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 132, 174–190.
- Ramos-Salgado, C., Muñuzuri, J., Aparicio-Ruiz, P., Onieva, L., 2022. A comprehensive framework to efficiently plan short and long-term investments in water supply and sewer networks. *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* 219, 108248.
- Rezvani, S., Almeida, N., Falcão, M., Duarte, M., 2022. Enhancing urban resilience evaluation systems through automated rational and consistent decision-making simulations. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 78, 103612.
- Ricalde, I., Vicuña, S., Melo, O., Tomlinson, J., Harou, J., Characklis, G., 2022. Assessing tradeoffs in the design of climate change adaptation strategies for water utilities in Chile. *J. Environ. Manag.* 302, 114035.
- Rising, J., Josset, L., Troy, T., Lall, U., 2022. The importance of infrastructure and national demand to represent constraints on water supply in the United States. *Global Environ. Change* 73, 102468.
- Rokstad, M., Ugarelli, R., 2015. Minimising the total cost of renewal and risk of water infrastructure assets by grouping renewal interventions. *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* 142, 148–160.
- Shafer, K., Fox, R., 2017. *An Equitable Water Future, A National Briefing Paper*. US Water Alliance.
- Toro, F., Ros, E., Mota, S., Ortega, J., 2006. Evolutionary algorithms for multiobjective and multimodal optimization of diagnostic schemes. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 53, 178–189.
- Trindade, B., Gold, D., Reed, P., Zeff, H., Characklis, G., 2020. Water pathways: An open source stochastic simulation system for integrated water supply portfolio management and infrastructure investment planning. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 132, 104772.
- Vieira, J., Cabral, M., Almeida, N., Silva, J., Covas, D., 2020. Novel methodology for efficiency-based long-term investment planning in water infrastructures. *Struct. Infrastructure Eng.* 16, 1654–1668.
- Vilarinho, H., Barbosa, F., Nóvoa, H., Silva, J., Yamada, L., Camanho, A., 2023a. Optimisation models for project selection in asset management: an application to the water sector. *Int. Trans. Oper. Res.*
- Vilarinho, H., D'Inverno, G., Nóvoa, H., Camanho, A., 2023b. The measurement of asset management performance of water companies. *Socio-Econ. Plan. Sci.* 87, 101545.
- Vilarinho, H., D'Inverno, G., Nóvoa, H., Camanho, A., 2023c. Performance analytics for regulation in retail water utilities: Guiding asset management by identifying peers and targets. *Util. Policy* 82, 101559.